

Eco-Social Ethics & Consumerism

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INTRODUCTION

Business is a part of the society. It functions in the society. So, it should be guided by the ethical or moral norms which the society wants the business to observe. In other words, every business should be guided by business ethics *i.e.*, moral principles which are considered by the society as right, and so, should govern and guide the activities of the business. In short, they are the moral principles and rules of conduct which should govern and guide the activities of a business. Business ethics require that the business should be conducted according to the recognized moral principles. Business ethics are derived from social values and laid down the norms of behavior for the business. By laying down the code of conduct, business ethics guide the businessmen in their business activities.

Concise Oxford Dictionary reads, "...a set of principles of morals, science of morals, moral principles, rules of conduct, the whole field of moral science." To more clear meaning, W.O.Wheeler remarked, "Business ethics is an art or science of maintaining a proper harmonious relationship with society and various groups and institutions as well as recognizing the moral responsibility for the rightness or wrongness of business conduct."

Zeno of Cyprus in third century B.C. discussed scientific systems of Ethics. It also means the correct knowledge of practical wisdom. So, the development process of the moral principles and codes of conduct is directly linked with the growth and development cycle of the society more or less depending upon the considerable points and time. In *Rig Veda*, a prayer for world peace was chanted. This is not the prayer only but the belief in the well being of all. "Let the universe be peaceful, the sky, air and atmosphere be pure, Sun, Moon and stars be peaceful, water, agriculture, cattle be peaceful; common man, the learned ones, the Brahmins be peaceful. Let all live in harmony".

This way, to achieve peaceful living, we need a common code of conduct. This common code of conduct measures all human being equal and gives joy and happiness naturally available to all. It is thus, called society *i.e.*, group leading an ethics or living a value based life enjoys the fruits of good organized living.

ECO-SOCIAL ETHICS

Eco-social ethics are those ethics which indicates towards the social as well as ecological, mainly, the environmental issues. In general parlance, business ethics simply means the responsibility of the business towards the general public and the society. But, if seen in a big perspective and given newer world, the meaning of ethics has molded towards the environment and society as a whole while doing business. Rapid industrialization, soil degradation, use of chemicals in agriculture, vast urbanization and erosion of producible land, deforestation, population explosion, use of hybrid seeds have made the situation unmanageable. Most of the business firms are more or less not aware about the environmental issues till today. Every business must maintain ethics pro-actively as numerated below:

- (a) Every business has to maintain healthy environmental condition in the place where its production is carried on by undertaking preventive and protective measures against air pollution, water pollution and noise pollution.
- (b) It must ensure the safety of the people in the surrounding areas. It must maintain cordial relations with the people of the surrounding areas.
- (c) It must create more employment opportunities for the people and must also provide medical facilities, educational facilities, recreational facilities, transport facilities etc. to the people of the society.
- (d) It must respect the philosophy of the country, such as freedom struggle, tolerance, non-violence, democratic setup, secularism, equallance, and political voting system.
- (e) It must play a direct role in promoting social welfare and must contribute to the national efforts to build up a better society and it must use the scarce resources efficiently without wastage and develop alternatives if necessary and seems such.
- (f) It must not indulge in anti-social activities like hoarding, black marketing etc. and must keep politics away from it.

Some of the companies have started showing awareness in adopting ethical issues as mentioned above. The most important of all the ethical issues is the increasing environmental damage and degradation. We all are concerned with this single issue of environment but the eco-social ethics issue is directly

related to the industrial development and technological development. All this development is being achieved on the cost of environment and society. Here, the issues of environmental degradation, resource depletion and air or water pollution are such issues that highly concern our future generations to come. Here, it is to note that the present theories of environment are concerned in the same manner to the future generations to come as they are to the present generation. We, in this very juncture, are directly related and responsible not only to the human being but to the natural world which comprises not only the human being but also other inhabitants of the nature, fauna, flora, ecosystem and non living things of the nature. Our responsibility is not only extended to selected one but to all of them also.

CONSUMERISM

Caveat Emptor is a term that makes the buyer beware during market sessions. The term is said to be obsolete now a days. But it is not so, the term is more relevant for present day consumer. In the era of globalization and hi-speed marketing and selling, it is not easy to examine all the goods and items before purchase. Moreover, during e-shopping, it becomes more difficult. Though, consumer protection is made easy. But after purchases it becomes troublesome to sue complaint and fight. It also exploits the consumer. Therefore, the precaution is better than the cure. Buyer without any exception is being misled, duped and deceived day in and day out.

Mahatma Gandhi, the father of nation, attached great importance to what he described as the "poor consumer", who according to him should be the principal beneficiary of the consumer movement. He said, "*A Consumer is the most important visitor on our premises. He is not dependent on us we are on him. He is not an interruption to our work; he is the purpose of it. We are not doing a favour to a consumer by giving him an opportunity. He is doing us a favour by giving an opportunity to serve him*".

Dictionary meaning of consumerism is used in two different contexts: *one*, as the protection and promotion of interests of consumers realized by such practices like product guarantee, hygienic production, honest packaging and advertising, improved safety standards, etc. and *two*, as the preoccupation of the society with the acquisition of goods believing in the theory that greater consumption of goods is economically beneficial. Here, for this research paper, I took consumerism as to mean somewhat in the latter sense. The main input for this, what I observed, is the consumption of goods is ethically beneficial. Further, I

want to register that the consumerism is not only the protection of the consumer or the production according to the needs of the consumers but also it also mean to produce, protect, and preserve the nature.

In the more liberalized and globalized form, consumerism is a universal and latest term of the new thinkers. In the words of the McMillan, "*Consumerism is concerned with protecting consumers from all organizations with which there is exchanged relationship. It encompasses the set of activities of government, business, independent organizations and concerned consumers that are designed to protect the rights of consumers*". In more general words – "*Consumerism is a movement or policies targeted at regulating the products and the services, methods or standards of manufactures, sellers, marketers and the buyers, such regulation may be institutional, statutory or embodied in a voluntary code occupied by a particular industry or it may result more indirectly from the influence of consumer organizations*".

CONCLUSION

Consumerism is an all pervasive term and more often misused only satisfying consumers while giving them value for money. In fulfilling consumer needs and requirements, companies' engagements have become limited to the production and redeem-out the grievances of the customers, if arising out of sale. But, the companies have forgotten their essential part towards the environmental and social values and responsibilities *i.e., however*, the eco-social ethics.

The material they are using, the methods they have adopted are how much anti-effective to the society and the environment is no concern for the present day companies. These issues are somewhat contributed by the consumerism-revolution. In this continuation, if we see the Chinese item, which have been rejected in bulk by a number of countries as they were harmful not only for the human being but also for the environment also.

The medical waste is another concern area for the society. Our hospitals have also converted to the big corporate houses and multi-type of medical waste is being produced by them, which must be properly disposed off.

In last, I want to conclude saying that the consumerism should have been led us to that extent from where it may become very difficult to come back. As we have generations to come, in acquiring consumerism and satisfying consumers, we pollute the world and it would become a no man's land.

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